

RCT- Effectiveness and NC bases of learning Tango Kids dance for autistic children with and without intellectual disabilities

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Antecedents:

Ruiz-Danegger, C. (2015a). Baile de Tango y Estudios Psicológicos (Tango Dance and Psychological Studies). DOI: [10.13140/RG.2.2.22344.74244](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22344.74244)

Ruiz-Danegger, C. (2015b). Tango dance, empathy, and perspective taking. DOI: [10.13140/RG.2.2.22344.74244](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22344.74244)

Ruiz-Danegger, C. (2015c). Performance de Tango argentino. Estilo: Milonga. DOI: [10.13140/RG.2.2.18150.43842](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18150.43842)

Ruiz-Danegger, C. (2015d). Performance de Tango argentino (estilo: Tango). DOI: [10.13140/RG.2.1.1396.1368](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.1396.1368)

Ruiz-Danegger (2016a). Performance de baile de tango. DOI: [10.13140/RG.2.2.29055.62881](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29055.62881)

Ruiz-Danegger (2016b). 10 years promoting development through play. DOI: [10.13140/RG.2.1.5071.2723](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.5071.2723)

Ruiz-Danegger (2017a). Flexibilization as a key- A reinterpretation of both the Karmiloff-Smith' & Baars-Dehaene-Naccache' models about development of consciousness. DOI: [10.13140/RG.2.2.29445.56803](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29445.56803)

Ruiz-Danegger, C. (2017b). Philosophy and science about dance. Preliminary considerations about its interdisciplinarity with Developmental Psychology. DOI: [10.13140/RG.2.2.12668.35203](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12668.35203)

C. Ruiz-Danegger has been dancing Argentine Tango since 2011. She was initiated by Masters Mercedes Tolaba and Luis Barraza, and served as a Tango dance teacher, under the supervision of her teacher. She learned about a variety of Tango dance contexts in her country (Argentina), as well as Barcelona and Paris. Constanza took classes with international Masters, and participated in collective events, such as Retiro Tanguero, local Festivals, or ETIs (“Encuentros Tangueros del Interior”, “Tango Meetings of the Inner Argentina”, massive meetings that take place throughout the country). Constanza also serves as certified Zumba Zumba™ Kids™ -Kids Jr™ Instructor.